

PAY SATISFACTION, EMOTIONAL LABOUR AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN EMOHUA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OF RIVERS STATE

¹Wadi Elizabeth Oghenetega and ²Samuel Aleruchi Egbuchu

Email: tegalizzy2009@yahoo.com

Phone: 08069374595

Phone: 08037408500

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Abstract

The need to ensure the wellbeing of teachers given their roles in the teaching pedagogy led to this study on the influence of pay satisfaction and emotional labour on the psychological wellbeing of teachers in secondary schools in Emohua local government area of Rivers State. Given the above, two research questions, objectives and hypotheses were raised to guide the study. Literature to understand what emotional labour, pay satisfaction and psychological wellbeing were exhausted. Given this justification, the affective events theory was used. Methodologically, the descriptive survey design became imperative for the study. The sample consisted of 350 teachers. The simple percentage, regression and ANOVA were used for data analysis. Based on the analysis, the first result stating that $F(1, 348) = 26.871, p < 0.05$, implies there is significant relationship as the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, Pay satisfaction significantly predicted the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State. Also, it was found that the regression analysis $F(1, 348) = 59.51, p < 0.05$, showed that emotional labour significantly influence the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State. Given the above result, the study recommended the need for teachers to be well paid or ensure pay satisfaction as such effort by the school authorities can aid the teachers because they will notice that their efforts and pay is commensurate.

1. Introduction

Teachers play a vital role in promoting education, learning and professional growth of learners, therefore, desire an ideal psychological wellbeing. They are more vulnerable to work-related stress, psychological distress and burnout than many other occupational groups (e.g. Johnson et al., 2005; Jones, Huxtable, Hodgson, & Price, 2003; Kyriacou, 2000). In order to develop more precisely targeted interventions to enhance well-being in the profession, insight is needed into the aspects of the teaching role that threaten psychological health of teachers.

^{1,2}Department Of Psychology Faculty of Social Sciences Rivers State University Port Harcourt Rivers State

Psychological wellbeing (PWB) of teachers is described as the judgement and satisfaction of an individual with his/her happiness, physical and mental health and profession (Huppert, 2009). To achieve this, two important variables were used by the researcher to study the influence of the psychological wellbeing of teachers. The first is pay satisfaction. Pay satisfaction refers to the “overall positive or negative feelings that individuals have towards their pay” (Miceli and Lane, 1991). Past research uni-dimension, scholars (Ellickson and Logsdon, 2002; Schwab & Wallace, 1974) has indicated that pay is one of the most important elements that can ensure ideal psychological wellbeing of workers given its economic factor that has significant relationship with staff productivity. Teaching job involves a high level of personal contact with the public, and also the performance of emotional labour. However, irrespective of the strategy used or the direction of this strategy, it is definite that teachers invest a certain degree of emotional effort in their jobs while trying to meet the necessities of displaying the apt emotions. Hence, the expression of emotion can no longer be regarded as a personal choice because it is akin to a market commodity where standards and rules govern how and when emotion should be displayed (Morris & Feldman, 1996). What’s more, there is considerable evidence that emotional labour can undermine employee well-being, as psychological effort is repeatedly required to regulate emotions in order to comply with organizational or professional rules (Grandey, 2000).

Teachers are expected to express different emotions during their interactions with students. They have to navigate between keeping a certain emotional distance or appear indifferent toward their students to safeguard a professional attitude on the one hand, and showing a sensitive, empathetic attitude on the other hand. When the teacher experiences a large discrepancy or dissonance between felt emotions and expected displays, the likelihood for impulsively expressing what one feels reduces and the need to act (whether deep or surface) increases accordingly.

Teachers are expected to ensure that their students are emotional and physically safe (Brennan, 2006). They are also expected to exemplify successful emotional control across situations, dealing with students with tenderness and empathy and repressing any feelings of irritation or resentment (Beatty, 2000). Hebson, Earnshaw, and Marchington (2007) contend that teachers are increasingly required to manage their emotions in like manner as employees in the service sector. Hence, the teaching role probably entails a considerable degree of emotional labour.

Campbell and Rothmann (2005) for example, defined emotional labour as the psychological processes required to regulate organizationally desired emotions that form an important part of one's job. Emotional labour has also been defined as the expressing and regulating affect or feelings in the workplace in order to conform to professional and organizational rules (Hochschild, 1983). Emotional labour involves the process of regulating the expression of emotions for achievement of organizational goals. As Emotional labour connote the process of managing the expression, it is similar to many concepts like deception, impression management, and dramaturgy. Thus, Liu, Perrewe, Hochwarter, & Kachmar, (2004) explained that emotional labour involves the attempt by individual to reduce the discrepancy between felt and displayed emotions. This therefore is what most teachers in Emohua LGA and other schools experiences. Sometimes they abandon their distress, pains and act as if they are better. This emotional management is instrumental for ideal teaching and learning. From the perspective of the individual service employee, emotional labour involves individual differences as well as individuals’ (re)interpretations of their emotional experiences when examining the causes and consequences of emotional labour. Individual differences may predispose individuals to feel and perceive stimuli in certain ways. Van Gelderen, Konijn and Bakker (2011)

state that emotional labour is especially pertinent for the human service professions, in which regular contact with clients forms an integral element of the job.

In Emohua LGA, there exist various secondary schools with various teaching staff. Observably, most teachers are often seen selling few products in the school and also leaving early from school. This may be a concern on poor pay structure and management not understanding the emotional labour each teacher passes through.

Teaching in secondary schools and other levels is characterized by intense emotional activity (Fernet et al., 2012); and other motivational processes such as pay satisfaction. This calls for the successful management of system and the knack to bring about the desired zeal and emotional state in others (Kinman et al., 2011). Teaching job can be said to be emotionally-laden in many ways. Teachers are expected to ensure that their students are emotional and physically safe (Brennan, 2006). They are also expected to exemplify successful emotional control across situations, dealing with students with tenderness and empathy and repressing any feelings of irritation or resentment (Beatty, 2000). Hebson, Earnshaw, and Marchington (2007) contend that teachers are increasingly required to manage their emotions in like manner as employees in the service sector. Hence, the teaching role probably entails a considerable degree of emotional labour. The teachers while doing this need to be treated like humans by helping them in terms of increasing their pays or salaries. Such motivation gives them satisfaction and recognition that makes them feel relieved from their emotional or psychological quagmire. Pointing further, teaching is a highly demanding profession with certain work-related experiences that can have negative effects on the general wellbeing of teachers (Chang 2009; Fernández-Berrocal et al. 2017). Maintaining teacher's psychological wellbeing is crucial not only for the teachers but for the success of their students and the school where they work (Jennings and Greenberg 2009). Therefore, the above issues led to this study on the influence of pay satisfaction and emotional labour on psychological wellbeing of teachers in secondary schools in Emohua local government area.

2. Statement of the Problem

Overtime, there is a growing body of evidence suggesting that jobs with pay dissatisfaction and those involving high amounts of emotional labour may have adverse consequences on the employees wellbeing, such as burnout (emotional exhaustion) (Brotheridge & Grandey 2002).

On the other hand, few studies existed on emotional labour, pay satisfaction and psychological wellbeing. Thus, none to the best knowledge of the researcher have been able to link the nexus. For example, a study by Olagunju et al (2020) titled *Psychosocial Wellbeing of Nigerian Teachers in Special Education Schools*, found that failed psychological wellbeing can compromise the effective performance of work-related roles. It further noted that increased burden predicted psychological distress, longer teaching experience was protective against distress. These findings underscore the need for motivation, inspire and support school teachers to enhance their wellbeing and roles. Therefore, implying that if the teacher's workload is not commensurate to the pay/salary, he/she may be dissatisfied and thereby affecting their psychological wellbeing.

In another study, Lee et al. (2012) researched on the relationship between job enjoyment and emotional labour with organizational support as the moderator of this relationship among 122 public relations employees (publicists) in various Taiwan region universities, who served as image makers who tries to enhance the public view of their organizations. However, organizational support did not moderate the relationship between job enjoyment and expression of naturally felt emotion. By implication, institutional support can emerge through pay satisfaction, good environment and noticing the emotional labour of the teacher.

Studies show that teachers fall into the category of workers who cope with a variety of work-related stresses, resulting in long-term physical and mental health issues, and increased burnout levels (Bernotaite et al. 2017; .

Skaalvik EM, Skaalvik, 2017). And these can affect the psychological wellbeing of teachers. This situation is not far from what is found among teachers in Emohua LGA, Rivers State and Nigeria at large.

Similarly, epidemiological reports indicate that teachers have mental health complications at a relatively higher rate than other professions, which may be due to their work stress, pupil-related difficulties, and interpersonal disputes with colleagues (Schonfeld, et al. 2017). However, in emerging countries like Nigeria, there are insufficient data about psychological health of teachers. Only a number of studies have reported the effect of psychological factors on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in Nigeria using different General Health Questionnaire (GHQ) assessment instruments (Akomolafe & Ogunmakin, 2014; Okwaraji et al. 2015, Ofovwe, et al. 2013; Ofili &, Usiholo, 2009).

In a study in the Benin City among teachers in private secondary schools, 17.2% of the dissatisfied teachers had psychological disorders, while 11.2% of the teachers who were satisfied had psychological disorders with a GHQ score greater than 4 (Ofili & Usiholo, 2009). Using GHQ-12, Okwaraji et al reported that 32.9% of the teachers had psychiatric morbidity in Enugu, Nigeria (Okwaraji, et al. 2015). In contrast, using GHQ-28, Ofovwe et al reported that 20.8% of the teachers in the Egor local government of the Edo State had a score of 4 or above, which indicated the presence of psychiatric disorders (Ofovwe, et al. 2013).

Finally, most studies explains that secondary school graduates' intellectual capacity is not different from that of school dropouts (Azi, 2016; . Akomolafe & Ogunmakin, 2014), that there is a low priority for treating mental health disorders in Nigeria, which has resulted in high levels of depression, anxiety, and depression among teachers; accordingly, it is supposed that teachers do not bother to seek care because of the stigmas and beliefs associated with psychological disorders in Nigeria (Azi & Lasebikan, 2016; Okpalauwaekwe, et al. 2017). Secondary education is in a very sensitive stage in Emohua LGA, Nigeria and in many developing countries. In addition, teaching in Nigeria is considered a part-time job until better offers or higher-paying jobs become available. Thus, it is important not to neglect teachers and to ensure that their salaries are satisfactory, and that their emotional labour are compensated as this will affect their psychological wellbeing positively.

Many studies related to psychological well-being have focused on students rather than on the health and well-being of teachers. It was as a result of the psychological crisis experienced by the teachers given an uncommensurated recognition of teachers efforts and its effects on students and society that prompted the study. Also, an extrapolation from various studies, a gap exist that prompted this study too. It was found that no study integrated the three variables and at same time carry such investigation among secondary school teachers psychological wellbeing. Against this backdrop led to this study that examine the influence of pay satisfaction and emotional labour on psychological wellbeing of teachers in Emohua LGA, Rivers State. Hence, the following research questions are given to guide the study.

- i. To what extent does pay satisfaction predict the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State?
- ii. To what extent does emotional labour predict the psychological wellbeing of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State?

Again, the researcher identified the following objectives of the study

- i. To investigate the extent pay satisfaction predict the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State.
- ii. To find out the extent emotional labour predict the psychological wellbeing of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

The researcher equally gave the following hypotheses to guide the study

- i. Pay satisfaction does not significantly predict the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State
- ii. Emotional labour does not significantly influence the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State.

3. Conceptual Review

Pay Satisfaction: The concept of pay satisfaction have never enjoyed the blessing of a universal acceptable definition. This implies that no single definition exists that explains this phenomena. Thus, pay has often been considered as a successful actual turnover (Bigliardi et al., 2005) approach to motivate the behaviour of employees. Present Pay satisfaction has been identified as an important day, contemporary organizations thus focus on ensuring indicator of an employee's intention to quit (Carless, 2005); that their employees are satisfied with their pay (Tekleab et al., 2005). It is believed that an individual's satisfaction refers to the "amount of overall positive or satisfaction with their pay generates a feeling of fair negative affect (or feelings) that individuals have toward their pay". Pay satisfaction is the amount of negative or positive feelings individuals have toward their pay. Although pay negative affect (or feeling) that individuals have toward satisfaction construct was originally measured as their pay" (Miceli and Lane, 1991). It can be defined as the amount of overall positive or negative affect (or feelings) that individuals have toward their pay.

Past research uni-dimension, scholars such as Ellickson and Logsdon (2002) has indicated that pay is one of the most important; and have then later dimensions linked with employee retention developed sub-scales for this construct. A major contribution was made by Heneman and Although studies (e.g., Tekleab et al., 2005; Schwab (1985) who presented pay satisfaction as a Williams et al., 2006) have empirically revealed a negative multidimensional construct and explicitly introduced the relationship between the satisfaction of individuals with concept.

Emotional Labour: Despite divergent opinions as to how Emotional Labour should be conceptualised, there is general agreement that Emotional Labour involves the management of emotions in order to conform to implicit or explicit display rules in organisations (Brotheridge & Grandey 2002; Brotheridge & Lee 2002; Diefendorff, Croyle & Gosserand 2005; Glomb & Tews 2004; Grandey 1999; Grandey 2003). Hochschild's (2003) conceptualization of emotional labour involves impression management of service employees. These employees put effort to express emotions acceptable by customers. According to this perspective, the discrepancy between felt and expressed emotion is related to job stress and burnout.

Emotional labour is typically conceptualised as the degree of dissonance between emotions that are genuinely felt and those that the job requires to be expressed or suppressed (Zapf et al., 1999). There is evidence that emotional labour can impair employee well-being, as psychological effort is frequently required to 'regulate' emotions in order to comply with organisational or professional expectations (Grandey, 2000). Mumby and Putnam (1992) conceptualized emotional labour as the way individuals change or manage emotions to make them appropriate or consistent with a situation, a role, or an expected organizational behavior. According to this view, expression of wider range of emotions at work is desirable, not to enhance productivity but to foster subjective well-being of the organizational members and their families.

Also, Ashforth and Humphrey (1993: 90) defined emotional labour as the act of displaying appropriate emotions, with the goal to engage in a form of impression management to foster social perceptions of her/himself as well as to foster an interpersonal climate (Gardner & Martinko, 1988). This conception of emotional labour focused mainly on the effectiveness of the behavior. As for Morris and Feldman (1996: 987), they conceptualized

emotional labour as the effort, planning, and control needed to express organizationally desired emotion during interpersonal transactions. This definition of emotional labour includes the organizational expectations for employees in their interactions with the customers, as well as the internal state of tension that occurs when a person displays emotions that are discrepant from her/his true feelings. They proposed that emotional labour consists of four dimensions: (a) frequency of interactions, (b) attentiveness (intensity of emotions, duration of interaction), (c) variety of emotions required and, (d) emotional dissonance. According to this perspective emotional labour is a characteristic of the job.

Teachers' emotional skills are critical to their own effectiveness and success as their work involves a significant potential for emotionally draining situations (Dorman, 2003). Compared to people working in other professions, a greater percentage of teachers report work as a source of stress and teachers who are stressed experience burnout, offer less information to students, are less accepting of student ideas, and interact less frequently with students and other colleagues. However, teachers who are more emotionally skilled at regulating their emotions tend to report less burnout and greater job satisfaction; they also experience greater positive affect while teaching and receive more support from students, colleagues and the principals with whom they work with (Brackett, et al. 2010). Positively expressed emotional labour also is at the core of the ability of school teachers to build and maintain positive and trusting relationships, as they spend more time on average dealing with learners and other individuals' problems than on any other work task (Patti and Tobin, 2006). For example, a teacher who accurately recognizes a student mild irritative behaviour during teaching and learning, experiences and understands the significance of the emotion will be better able both to predict the learner's subsequent actions and respond appropriately to the learner (Elfenbein and Ambady, 2002).

How well a teacher expresses emotional labour and regulates emotions is critical to the relationship with learners, ability to dispense knowledge efficiently and be job satisfied. One angry outburst can destroy a teacher-students, teacher-teachers and teacher-principals (head of schools) relationship forever. Carmeli and Josman (2006) in their investigation of the relationship among emotional labour, task performance and organizational citizenship behaviours reported that individuals who are high in emotional labour are likely to exhibit a higher level of performance outcomes and job satisfaction.

Psychological Wellbeing: Conceptually, psychological well-being refers to positive mental health. Research has shown that psychological well-being is a diverse multidimensional concept (Ryff, 1989), which develops through a combination of emotional regulation, personality characteristics, identity and life. Psychological well-being can increase with age, education, extraversion and consciousness and decreases with neuroticism (Keyes et al., 2002). In terms of gender, research has suggested that there is no significant difference between men and women on measures of psychological well-being. Furthermore, the perception of physical health and spirituality can mediate the relationship between context and psychological wellbeing (Temane & Wissing, 2006a, 2006b).

Psychological well-being has undergone extensive empirical review and theoretical evaluation (Wissing & Van Eeden, 1998). There is currently no single consensual conceptual understanding of psychological well-being. Initial understanding of psychological well-being provided a depiction of the difference between positive and negative affect. Preliminary research was mainly concerned with the experiences of positive and negative affect, subjective well-being and life satisfaction that were formed around the Greek word 'eudemonia', which was translated as 'happiness' (Ryff, 1989b). Happiness was described as the equilibrium between positive and negative affect. Many early scales, such as Satisfaction with Life Scale on which a vast amount of research was conducted, used this initial subjective conception of well-being (Conway & Macleod, 2002;). The Satisfaction with Life Scale requires participants to indicate a cognitive rather than affective response in relation to global

satisfaction with their quality of life. Despite extensive evaluation and assessments, experts have indicated that psychological well-being is a diverse multidimensional concept, with exact components still unknown (Wissing & Van Eeden, 2002).

4. Theoretical Framework

The paper is anchored on *affective events theory*. The Affective Events Theory (AET) was propounded by Weiss and Cropanzano's (1996). The Affective Events Theory (AET) provides a useful framework to study the antecedents and consequences of affective states in the workplace. The AET was propounded to explain how work environments influence the affective and evaluative response of the employee. The AET is based on the premise that characteristics of the work environment predispose the occurrence of certain work events, which lead to specific emotions (affective reactions), which in turn shape work attitudes and behaviours (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996).

However, the intensity of this effect brought about by an event is somewhat dependent on personality dispositions and mood. While some people are more vulnerable to negative events and react strongly against them, others may remain unruffled and confident. In other words, events that transpire at work, depending on the work environment and the personality traits of the individual, may lead to emotional reactions. According to the AET, a single event, which elicits an emotional reaction, also instigates a sequence of subsequent emotional experiences operating in a cause-effect relationship. Emotions are usually characterized as affective, fleeting relatively intense, and they usually interrupt thought processes (George, 1996). Hence, events may occur within work environments that act as "affective shocks" to the existing system (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996), that is, they require additional interpretation and reaction. When physical and emotional reactions are cumulated over time, they are proposed to affect the overall feelings one has about the job (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996).

AET states that features of the job make the occurrence of certain types of work events more possible than others. These discrete events, called affective events, are then thought to lead to particular affective reactions (i.e., emotions) at work. Affective reactions, in turn, are proposed to lead to both immediate, affect-driven behaviours (e.g., smiling, frowning, yelling) and also to contribute to work attitudes in the long run (such as job satisfaction). Drawing on the AET to explain emotional labour – psychological wellbeing relations among teachers, for example, certain occurrences in the classroom such as an overly stubborn and troublesome student who constantly constitutes a nuisance in the class by trying to distract other students, inattentive, making noise, bullying, refusing to do assignments and so on, could be considered affective events. Such events might evoke an affective reaction or emotion (e.g., anger, embarrassment) in the teacher, which results in affect-driven behaviours, such as frowning, yelling at the student, or punishing the student.

However, it may require that the teacher performs emotional labour to regulate his or her own emotion in accordance with the display rules of the school. Thus, the teacher may use surface acting to suppress emotions like frustration, irritation, anger, or tension due to the student's misbehaviour. And the consequences of sustained suppression of these negative emotions may impair the health of teacher over time (i.e., it may lead to burnout). The theory suggests that in the long run and repeated occurrences of this type of event, the teacher's job satisfaction might be expected to decrease, as a function of the increased negative emotions experienced at work. According to the theory, affective states are proposed to directly influence work attitudes and affect-driven behaviours, whereas it is work attitudes that lead to judgment-driven behaviours. In other words, affective states are suggested to have a direct influence on affect driven behaviours, but an indirect influence – mediated through work attitudes – on judgment-driven behaviors. For example, a teacher may smile even though he or she is depressed, or they may try to appear polite even though they are very angry with certain students.

Linking the theory to the situation of teachers in secondary schools in Emohua local government area, what the AET implies in terms of the teaching profession is that the extent of emotional labour that teachers perform as part of the requirements of their job is contingent on the events that occur at work. As such, the more positive the events are, the less likely the performance of emotional labour and vice versa. This is because negative events create emotions that are discrepant from the organizationally desired ones, employees who frequently experience negative events may have to suppress their negative emotions by performing surface acting (Mignonac & Herrbach, 2004). Following the arguments made by the AET (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996), it stands to reason, then, that if teachers truly feel the emotions that they express to students, they should feel less exhausted and therefore less likely to depersonalize the students. In other word, frequent experiences of negative events at work may result in negative outcomes such as psychological crisis. To encourage the teacher to boost his performance and ensuring psychological wellbeing, there is need for motivation through pay satisfaction.

5. Methodology

The paper adopted a descriptive survey design. The design is imperative in expressing the phenomenon. The population of the study constitutes 978 (Emohua LGA, School Board, 2022) teachers found in the twenty four (24) secondary schools in Emohua local government area. Given this, the convenience sampling technique was used to select only 350 teachers and fourteen schools. In each school, it has junior and secondary section. In each section, quota sampling technique was used to allocate 7 samples across. Some of the schools are Uvuawu comprehensive high school, Ibaa; Community secondary School Rumuji; Ibaa girls secondary school, Community Secondary School Ndele and Community Secondary School Emohua, etc. Both primary and secondary sources of data collection were utilized. The simple percentage, regression and ANOVA were used for analysis.

6. Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Participant Characteristics

Variables	Frequency	%
Gender		
Male	152	43
Female	198	57
Age		
Below 45years	164	47
Above 46years	186	53
Educational Attainment		
NCE/OND/HND/Bachelor's Degree	152	43
Postgraduate Degree	198	57
Marital Status		
Married	229	65
Single	79	23
Divorced	42	12
Years of Experience		
Below 15years	187	53
Above 16years	163	47
Total	350	100

Source: Research Fieldwork, 2022

This study included 350 teachers in the Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Table 1 shows that 57% of the teachers were female while 43% were male, 53% fell in the above 46 years age bracket while 47% were in the below 45years bracket, 43% had either NCE/OND/HND or a Bachelor’s degree while 57% has postgraduate degrees, 65% were married, 23% single while 12% were divorced. 53% had less than 15years of work experience while 47% had over 16years of work experience.

Research Questions

Research Question One: To what extent does pay satisfaction predict the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Table 2: Model Summary of Regression Analysis of Pay Satisfaction on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.268	.072	.069	3.32151

Table 2. shows an R-value of .268, R² value of .072 and an Adjusted R² value of .069. From the above-stated result, pay satisfaction accounted for 6.9% of the variance observed in the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State.

Research Question Two: To what extent does emotional labour predict the psychological wellbeing of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Table 3: Model Summary of Regression Analysis of Emotional Labour on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
	.382	.146	.144	3.18572

Table 3. shows an R-value of .382, R² value of .146 and an Adjusted R² value of .144. From the above-stated result, emotional labour accounted for 14% of the variance observed in the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: Pay satisfaction does not significantly predict the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Table 4: ANOVA Associated with Regression Summary of Pay Satisfaction on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	296.427	1	296.427	26.869	.000 ^b
Residual	3839.287	348	11.032		
Total	4135.714	349			

Table 5: Coefficients Associated with Regression Summary of Pay Satisfaction on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	27.101	1.682		16.111	.000
Pay Satisfaction	.231	.045	.268	5.184	.000

Table 5 shows the result of an ANOVA associated with regression analysis testing the significance. It shows $F(1, 348) = 26.871, p < 0.05$. This result is significant as the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 5 shows the b-coefficients of our regression model [*Psychological well-being* = 27.10 + .231.*Pay*

Satisfaction]. The result thus suggests that pay satisfaction positively impacts the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA (p values 0.000, $\beta = .268$). This result suggests that pay satisfaction significantly predicts the psychological well-being of teachers in Ikwerre Local Government Area of Rivers State. Hence the null hypothesis is **rejected**.

Given the importance of pay satisfaction, study by Ikuru (2021) saw it as an economic factor that motivate a worker. Hence, if workers/teachers found that the pay is satisfactory may desire to seek for more professional development to improve his status and at the same time benefiting the students and the society. Also, it was found in some studies that employee satisfaction with their pay can be a factor that may help organizations (including teachers) to retain skilled workers. It was indicated that high turnover is a hindrance to achieving high levels of productivity an efficiency. When the teachers or organizational staff are discouraged, the institution or organizations not only lose their valuable employees but it is also expensive since it requires managers to spend resources; time and money, on the recruitment and training of the replacements of those who quit (Derry & Shaw, 1999, Juhdi et al., 2013).

Hypothesis Two: Emotional labour does not significantly influence the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Table 6: ANOVA Associated with Regression Summary of Emotional Labour on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	603.929	1	603.929	59.507	.000 ^b
Residual	3531.786	348	10.149		
Total	4135.714	349			

Table 8: Coefficients Associated with Regression Summary of Emotional Labour on Psychological Well-being of Teachers in Emohua LGA of Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
(Constant)	49.171	1.745		28.173	.000
Emotional Labour	-.376	.049	-.382	-7.714	.000

Table 6 shows the result of an ANOVA associated with regression analysis testing the significance. It shows $F(1, 348) = 59.51, p < 0.05$. This result is significant as the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Table 8 shows the b-coefficients which dictates our regression model [$Psychological\ well-being = 49.17 - .376 \cdot Emotional\ Labour$]. The result thus suggests that emotional labour inversely impacts the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua LGA (p values 0.000, $\beta = -.382$). This result suggests that emotional labour significantly predicts the psychological well-being of teachers in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Hence the null hypothesis is **rejected**.

The findings of this study is in consonance with that of Brackett et al. (2010) that supports the stand that teachers who are more emotionally skilled at regulating their emotions tend to report less burnout and greater job satisfaction; they also experience greater positive effect while teaching and receive more support from students, colleagues and the principals with whom they work with. Also, the findings of Patti and Tobin (2006) relates with the present study as it explained that positively expressed emotional labour also is at the core of the ability of school teachers to build and maintain positive and trusting relationships, as they spend more time on average dealing with learners and other individuals' problems than on any other work task. The example given by

Elfenbein and Ambady (2002) is linked to this study as it explains that a teacher who accurately recognizes a student's mild irritative behaviour during teaching and learning, experiences and understands the significance of the emotion will be better able both to predict the learner's subsequent actions and respond appropriately to the learner. In all, the present study found that how well a teacher expresses emotional labour and regulates emotions is critical to the relationship with learners, ability to dispense knowledge efficiently and be job satisfied. This is because the findings of the second hypothesis reveals that teachers' with high emotional labour have positive attitude to teaching and will exhibit high level of psychological wellbeing job satisfaction, $F(1, 348) = 59.51, p < 0.05$.

On this, the study by Mukundan and Ahour (2011) Brouwers et al., (2011) proved that emotional exhaustion, in the teaching profession, that occurs when the teacher feels weary and fatigued that manifests when emotional energies are depleted. Consequently, they explained that the teachers if discover that they can no longer give their best to students as they do before, the teacher may become physically and mentally exhausted. Which can result to students' negative reactions and attitudes toward the teacher in particular and the learning situation in general. As for Hebson, Earnshaw and Marchington (2007), they contend that teachers are increasingly required to manage their emotions in like manner as employees in the service sector. Hence, the teaching role probably entails a considerable degree of emotional labour.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study was conducted to investigate pay satisfaction, emotional labour as correlates of psychological wellbeing among secondary school teachers in Emohua local government area of Rivers State, Nigeria. According to the findings of this study, a significant correlation was established between both pay satisfaction and psychological wellbeing. Furthermore, there was a significant negative relationship between emotional labour and psychological wellbeing. Given the outcome of this study whose intention is to ensure the wellbeing of workers, these findings would help stakeholders in the educational system to provide significant incentives for improving teachers, welfare through pay satisfaction and other means that can ensure job satisfaction as these have significant effect on the psychological wellbeing of teachers in secondary school. In the light of this, the following are recommended:

- Management of education to ensure that school environment should be made convenient enough and essential patronage be given to teachers to enable them do extremely well in their daily teaching and learning interactive experience with students.
- It may be beneficial to train teachers (e.g., by means of workshops) on how to use reappraisal strategies to modify their experiences of (negative) emotions and prevent the overreliance on hiding undesirable emotions and faking the desirable ones.
- There is need for the teachers' to be given professional development through conferences, training and workshops that would help them develop the capacity to cope with modern pedagogical teaching style as to avoid anxiety that may ensue due to lack of competence in its management. Through this effort, teachers can manage emotional distress that sprout from some unscrupulous student's behaviour.
- Teachers need to be well paid or ensure pay satisfaction. Such efforts by the school authorities can aid the teachers because they will notice that their efforts and pay are commensurate. Such will inspire, elevate, motive and drive their zeal to perform optimally and also usher then the ability to avoid the experience of job strain.
- Supportive workplace environment and workplace social support might protect teachers against the negative impact of emotional labour on well-being.

- Finally, the paper recommends that factors that can promote the psychological wellbeing of teachers should be identified, explored and utilised.

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